

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Endophytic *Metarhizium robertsii* improves maize performance and suppresses the feeding activity of the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 12/10/2025

Accepted: 25/11/2025

Keywords

Endophytic entomopathogenic fungi, *Metarhizium* and *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Abstract

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) of the genus *Metarhizium* are well-recognized for their potential as biological control agents against a wide range of agricultural pests. Beyond their entomopathogenic role, recent studies have highlighted their capacity to establish endophytic associations with plants, thereby promoting growth and enhancing plant defense mechanisms. In this study, we investigated the endophytic colonization ability of two *Metarhizium robertsii* isolates in maize (*Zea mays*) and evaluated their effects on plant growth and resistance against the fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J. E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Conidial suspensions (1×10^8 conidia/mL) were applied through seed soaking and soil drenching. Plant growth parameters, including height, shoot dry biomass, and chlorophyll content, were assessed alongside the feeding performance of *S. frugiperda* neonates on colonized plants. Both *M. robertsii* isolates successfully established as endophytes within maize tissues. While plant height and biomass were not significantly influenced by fungal inoculation or application method, chlorophyll content was notably increased in plants colonized by both isolates. Moreover, *S. frugiperda* larvae feeding on colonized plants exhibited significantly reduced weight gain, indicating a negative impact on insect performance. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that *M. robertsii* isolates can function as beneficial endophytes in maize, enhancing physiological performance and modulating plant defense against *S. frugiperda*. Further research is warranted to elucidate the underlying mechanisms driving these plant–fungus–insect interactions.

Introduction

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) are widely recognized as effective and environmentally sustainable alternatives to conventional synthetic insecticides within integrated pest management (IPM) programs (Faria and Wraight, 2007;

Sharma *et al.*, 2023 and Rajput *et al.*, 2024). In addition to their established role as external biocontrol agents, numerous EPF species are now known to establish endophytic associations with a wide range of host plants, providing multiple agronomic benefits (Parsa *et al.*, 2013 and

Vega, 2018). Such endophytic interactions have been reported to enhance plant growth, improve tolerance to abiotic stress, and strengthen plant defenses against insect herbivores (Behie *et al.*, 2012; Bamisile *et al.*, 2018 and Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). Notably, colonization of maize by *Metarhizium* and *Beauveria* species has been linked to improved plant performance, including increased height, chlorophyll content, and biomass accumulation (Kabaluk and Ericsson, 2007; Liao *et al.*, 2014 and 2017). Moreover, these fungi can contribute to plant defense by mediating direct and indirect interactions with herbivores, often through the priming of host immune responses and alterations in plant biochemical pathways (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020; Baron *et al.*, 2020 and García-Espinoza *et al.*, 2023).

Endophytic entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) naturally inhabit the plant rhizosphere and are capable of colonizing internal plant tissues without inducing visible harm to their hosts (Vega, 2018 and Bamisile *et al.*, 2021). To promote their successful establishment within plants, several artificial inoculation techniques have been developed, including seed treatment, root dipping, and soil application, each designed to optimize fungal delivery and colonization efficiency (Mahanty *et al.*, 2017; Bamisile *et al.*, 2021 and González-Guzmán *et al.*, 2021). The efficacy of these methods often depends on both the fungal species and the host plant involved. For example, leaf inoculation with conidial suspensions has proven most effective for *Beauveria bassiana* colonization in sorghum, stem injection for coffee, and root dipping for tomato (Bamisile *et al.*, 2018). Successful inoculation not only increases the likelihood of endophytic establishment but also confers several downstream benefits, including the induction of systemic resistance against insect pests and phytopathogens, as well as enhanced plant growth and productivity (Muvea *et al.*,

2014; Qayyum *et al.*, 2015 and González-Guzmán *et al.*, 2021).

Maize (*Zea mays*) is one of the world's most important cereal crops, serving as a staple food, animal feed, and industrial raw material (Nuss and Tanumihardjo, 2010 and Ranum *et al.*, 2014). However, its production is increasingly threatened by invasive lepidopteran pests, particularly the fall armyworm (FAW), *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J. E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Ayra-Pardo and Borrás-Hidalgo, 2019). This highly polyphagous species feeds on more than 350 plant species, with a strong preference for grasses such as maize (Casmuz *et al.*, 2010 and Montezano *et al.*, 2019). Several studies have demonstrated the high virulence of *Metarhizium* spp. against *S. frugiperda*. For instance, *Metarhizium rileyi* has shown strong pathogenicity under laboratory conditions, where even low conidial densities (4×10^3 conidia/cm²) caused more than 95% larval mortality within eight days. Similarly, greenhouse applications using either aqueous conidial suspensions or dry conidial powder (6.3×10^6 conidia per plant) achieved mortality rates of 88–96%. However, field applications of unformulated conidial sprays at $0.6\text{--}1.2 \times 10^{12}$ conidia/ha resulted in considerably lower efficacy, with larval mortality reduced to 27–31% (Faria *et al.*, 2022). These discrepancies between laboratory, greenhouse, and field outcomes highlight the challenges of deploying EPF under natural conditions. Environmental stressors such as ultraviolet radiation, low relative humidity, and temperature fluctuations can substantially compromise fungal viability, persistence, and infectivity (Butt and Goettel, 2000). Thus, exploiting EPF as endophytes represents a promising field-deployable strategy to overcome these limitations, providing more consistent pest suppression while promoting plant health. This dual functionality highlights the potential of endophytic EPF (EPPF) as sustainable agents that enhance plant vigor and reduce herbivore performance.

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effects of two inoculation methods on *Metarhizium robertsii* colonization and to assess how such colonization influences key maize growth parameters and the feeding performance of *S. frugiperda* larvae.

Materials and methods

1. Insect rearing:

Eggs of *S. frugiperda* were maintained in 500 mL plastic containers and monitored daily under controlled laboratory conditions until hatching. Newly emerged neonates were gently transferred individually into 1-oz rearing cups ($4.5 \times 3.0 \times 3.8 \text{ cm}^3$; Frontier Agricultural Sciences, Newark, DE, USA) using a fine-tipped paintbrush. Larvae were reared on a wheat germ- and casein-based artificial diet prepared according to the formulation described by Peiffer and Felton (2005). Upon pupation, pupae were collected and placed in 2L glass jars lined with paper towels. After adult emergence, sterile cotton balls soaked in a 10% honey solution were suspended from the jar lid as a food source, and strips of white paper were provided as oviposition substrates. All developmental stages were maintained at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 50–70% relative humidity (R.H.), and a 16:8 h (L:D) photoperiod.

2. Fungal isolates:

2.1. Origin and identification of fungal isolates:

Two *Metarhizium robertsii* isolates (50 and 75) used in this study were obtained from the Department of Entomology, College of Agricultural Sciences, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, USA. The isolates were originally recovered from soil samples collected in winter canola (*Brassica napus* var. *Wichita*) plots using the *Galleria mellonella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) insect baiting method. Before experimental use, each isolate was passed through *G. mellonella* larvae to restore virulence. Fungal cultures were subsequently maintained on Sabouraud dextrose agar supplemented with yeast extract (SDAY) following

standard procedures (Ansari and Butt, 2011 and Inglis *et al.*, 2012).

2.2. Fungal conidia production:

Fungal conidia were mass-produced using a solid substrate fermentation method, as described by Jaronski and Jackson (2012). Initially, five 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing Sabouraud dextrose yeast broth (SDYB) were each inoculated with a 0.8 cm agar plug from 7-day-old SDAY cultures. These flasks were incubated on an orbital shaker at 150 rpm for 5 days at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ to establish liquid pre-cultures. For solid-state cultivation, 200 g of broken rice were soaked in 100 mL of distilled water for 2 hours and transferred into 500 mL autoclavable mushroom spawn bags ($20 \times 19.69 \times 19 \text{ cm}$). The bags were autoclaved at 121°C and 1.5 atm for 55 minutes, then cooled and inoculated with 20 mL of fungal slurry. Bags were manually shaken to ensure uniform distribution of the inoculum and incubated in complete darkness at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 14 days. Conidia were harvested by washing the dried rice with sterile distilled water containing 0.03% (v/v) Tween 80. The resulting suspensions were serially diluted and quantified using a Neubauer hemocytometer to adjust the number of conidia to 1×10^8 conidia/mL for further experiments. Germination rates were assessed, and only conidial batches with $\geq 95\%$ germination were used in subsequent bioassays (Inglis *et al.*, 2012).

3. Response of maize plants to fungal treatments:

3.1. Plant growth medium preparation:

The plant growth medium was prepared by mixing field soil collected from the Lake Erie Regional Grape Research and Extension Center with a commercial organic potting mix (Vigoro Industries, Inc., Northbrook, IL, USA) in a 1:1 ratio (v/v). To reduce microbial contamination, the soil-potting mix blend was sterilized twice by autoclaving at 121°C for 2 hours. After 48 hours, the sterilized growth medium was transferred into 2.5 L plastic pots for subsequent plant cultivation.

3.2. Seed disinfection and inoculation:

Sweet corn seeds (Hoss, Norman Park, GA, USA) were surface sterilized by immersion in 0.05% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for 2 minutes, followed by 70% ethanol for 2 minutes, then rinsed three times in sterile distilled water and air-dried on sterile tissue paper under laminar airflow in a biosafety cabinet. To confirm the efficacy of surface sterilization, 100 μ L of the final rinse water was plated onto SDAY and incubated to detect potential microbial contaminants, as described by Ahmad *et al.* (2020).

Two inoculation methods, seed soaking and soil drenching, were employed to inoculate maize seeds. For seed soaking, maize seeds were immersed in a conidial suspension (1×10^8 conidia mL^{-1}) and agitated on a rotary shaker for 2 hrs. The treated seeds were then sown individually in 2.5L plastic pots at a depth of 2–2.5 cm using a sterile spatula. For soil drenching, a single surface-sterilized maize seed was sown per pot under the same conditions, after which 5 mL of the conidial suspension (1×10^8 conidia mL^{-1}) was applied directly to the soil surrounding the seed. Control pots received either seeds soaked in 0.03% (v/v) aqueous Tween 80 or soil drenched with 5 mL of sterile 0.03% (v/v) aqueous Tween 80 solution without fungal conidia. Fifteen replicate pots were prepared for each fungal treatment. All pots were maintained in a controlled-environment growth chamber at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 70% relative humidity, and a 16:8 hrs. light: dark photoperiod, with 70% light intensity. Plants were watered as needed to maintain optimal soil moisture.

3.3. Detection of endophytic fungal colonization in maize tissues:

Endophytic colonization by *M. robertsii* was assessed in maize plants at the V3 growth stage. The third fully expanded leaf and two sections of the root system were gently excised and rinsed with tap water to remove adhering soil particles. Surface sterilization was performed as described previously (Section 3, b). Plant tissues were

subsequently dried under sterile laminar airflow. Sterilized leaf sections were cut into 0.5×0.5 cm squares, and root segments were cut into 1 cm lengths using sterile dissecting scissors. Processed tissues were then plated on SDAY in labeled Petri dishes. Plates were sealed and incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in darkness for 10 days. Fungal outgrowth from internal tissues was monitored and recorded. Colonization was confirmed based on the morphological characteristics of *M. robertsii*.

3.4. Plant height and above-ground biomass:

At the V3 growth stage, plant height was measured as the distance from the base of the stem at the soil surface to the tip of the most fully emerged true leaf using a ruler. For above-ground biomass determination, plants were harvested by cutting at the soil surface using sterile scissors, excluding the third leaf. The harvested shoots were placed into pre-weighed, pre-dried paper bags and oven-dried at 50°C for 10–14 days until a constant dry biomass was achieved.

3.5. Chlorophyll content:

Chlorophyll content was estimated by extracting pigments from a 1 cm^2 disc of maize leaf at the V3 stage. The tissue was homogenized in 80% acetone and centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 30 minutes. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 663 nm and 645 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, and total chlorophyll content was calculated following the method described by Shah *et al.* (2018).

3.6. Larval feeding performance:

Fresh leaf tissue (0.5 g) was excised from treated and control plants and placed on 4 mL of 2% agar at the base of individual plastic rearing cups. Newly hatched *S. frugiperda* neonates were transferred individually to each cup using a fine brush. After five days of feeding, larval weight was measured using an analytical balance.

4. Statistical analysis:

The entire experiment was independently repeated twice under identical environmental and experimental

conditions. All datasets were analyzed using a general linear model (GLM) to evaluate the effects of treatments. Prior to analysis, data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variances to ensure compliance with model assumptions. When significant differences were detected ($p < 0.05$), pairwise comparisons among treatment means were conducted using Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test. All statistical analyses were performed using Minitab statistical software (version 3.2.5).

Results and discussion

1. Effect of fungal treatments on maize plants:

Maize plants inoculated with *M. robertsii* isolates using either seed soaking or soil drenching at a concentration of 1×10^8

conidia mL^{-1} exhibited successful endophytic colonization by the two fungal isolates. The frequency of fungal recovery from plant tissues varied depending on the fungal isolation and the inoculation method employed. Among the different plant parts, the roots exhibited the highest colonization rates, particularly in plants inoculated via soil drench (Figure 1). The highest percentage of root colonization was recorded in plants treated with *M. robertsii* isolate 75 (69.23%), followed by those treated with isolate 50 (46.15%). In contrast, seed-inoculated plants exhibited lower colonization frequencies, with 37.55% and 33.3% colonization for isolates 75 and 50, respectively (Table 1). No fungal colonization was detected in the control plants.

Table (1): Percentage of fungal recovery from treated and control maize plants (Root tissue) at the V3 growth stage. Fungus was detected in at least one of the tested tissue samples.

Treatment	Colonization Rate %	
	Soil Drench	Seeds Inoculation
Control	0	0
<i>Metarhizium robertsii</i> (Isolate 50)	46.15%	33.3%
<i>Metarhizium robertsii</i> (Isolate 75)	69.23%	37.5%

Figure (1): Re-isolation of fungal entomopathogens from maize roots as endophytes.

1.1. Plant height and above-ground biomass:

Treatment of maize seeds with conidial suspensions of *M. robertsii* isolates 50 and 75, applied either through seed soaking or soil drenching at 1×10^8 conidia mL^{-1} , did not significantly affect plant height or aboveground biomass compared with control plants treated with Tween 80 (0.03%, v/v). At the V3 growth stage, the mean plant heights were 63.65 ± 1.37 cm for control, 63.12 ± 1.63 cm for isolating 50, and 64.84 ± 1.90 cm for isolating 75 following soil drench inoculation. For seed inoculation, mean plant heights were 65.00 ± 1.36 cm for control, 64.72 ± 1.62 cm for isolate 50, and 64.37 ± 1.91 cm for isolate 75 (Figure 2a). Statistical analysis indicated no

significant effects of inoculation method ($p=0.574$), fungal isolation ($p=0.895$), or their interaction ($p=0.840$). Similarly, fungal inoculation had no significant impact on shoot dry biomass, although a slight, non-significant increase was observed in treated plants. For soil drench applications, mean shoot dry weights were 0.57 ± 0.29 g for control, 0.67 ± 0.29 g for isolate 50, and 0.79 ± 0.48 g for isolate 75. Seed inoculation yielded dry biomass values of 0.78 ± 0.48 g and 0.67 ± 0.45 g for isolates 50 and 75, respectively (Figure 2b). Differences among inoculation methods ($p=0.740$), fungal isolates ($p=0.677$), and their interaction ($p=0.530$) were not statistically significant.

Figure (2): Effect of soil drenching and seed soaking with *Metarhizium robertsii* isolates 50 and 75 (1×10^8 conidia mL^{-1}) on maize plant height and shoot dry biomass compared with the control. (a) Plant height was measured at the V3 growth stage following soil drench or seed soaking treatments. (b) Shoot dry biomass of maize plants at the V3 stage after drying at 50°C for 10–14 days.

1.2. Chlorophyll content:

Maize plants grown in soil treated with *M. robertsii* isolate 75 exhibited significantly higher chlorophyll content compared with both isolate 50 and the control ($p < 0.001$). Treatment with isolate 75 increased chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll to 20.93 ± 0.78 , 8.77 ± 0.49 , and 29.69 ± 1.21 mg mL^{-1} , respectively. In contrast, plants treated with

isolate 50 recorded 16.10 ± 0.67 , 5.80 ± 0.28 , and 21.23 ± 0.94 mg mL^{-1} , while the control plants exhibited 13.78 ± 0.56 , 6.32 ± 0.24 , and 22.61 ± 0.80 mg mL^{-1} for chlorophyll a, b, and total chlorophyll, respectively (Figure 3). For seed inoculation, no significant differences were observed among treatments. The chlorophyll a, b, and total chlorophyll contents were 16.57 ± 0.79 , 6.73 ± 0.98 , and 23.30 ± 1.01 mg mL^{-1} for

the control; 21.93 ± 0.79 , 6.03 ± 0.42 , and 22.55 ± 1.43 mg mL⁻¹ for isolate 50; and 18.40 ± 1.22 , 7.07 ± 1.39 , and 25.46 ± 1.42 mg mL⁻¹ for isolate 75 (Figure 3). Statistical analysis revealed a significant effect of fungal isolate and the interaction between fungal isolate and inoculation method ($p <$

0.001), whereas the inoculation method alone had no significant influence ($p > 0.05$). These findings indicate that isolate 75 enhanced chlorophyll accumulation and may promote improved photosynthetic performance in maize.

Figure (3): Effect of soil drenching and seed soaking with *Metarhizium robertsii* isolates 50 and 75 (1×10^8 conidia mL⁻¹) on the chlorophyll content of maize plants at the V3 growth stage compared with the control. (A) Chlorophyll a, (B) chlorophyll b, and (C) total chlorophyll content (mg mL⁻¹) in maize leaves following treatment with different inoculation methods.

2. Effect of maize-colonized plants on *S. frugiperda* neonate development:

The weight gained by *S. frugiperda* neonates was significantly different after five days of feeding on V3-stage maize plants grown in soil treated with different fungal strains ($p < 0.001$). Neonates that

were fed on plants grown in soil treated with *M. robertsii* isolate 50 and isolate 75 exhibited the lowest weight gain, which was significantly reduced compared to the untreated control (Figure 4).

Figure (4): Effect of *Metarhizium robertsii* isolates 50 and 75 on the weight gain of *Spodoptera frugiperda* neonates after five days of feeding on maize plants at the V3 growth stage. Maize plants were grown in soil treated with 1×10^8 conidia mL^{-1} of fungal isolates.

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) are primarily soil-borne microorganisms that inhabit the rhizosphere and can establish mutualistic associations within plant tissues. These fungi are widely recognized for their role as biological control agents against diverse arthropod pests (Shah and Pell 2003 and Gao *et al.*, 2011). In recent years, research has increasingly focused on exploiting EPF as endophytes acting as eco-friendly biocontrol and biostimulant agents to suppress pest populations and phytopathogens while simultaneously improving crop performance and resilience (Kumar *et al.*, 2022 and Fite *et al.*, 2023).

In the present study, two *M. robertsii* isolates were evaluated for their ability to colonize maize plants through two application methods, seed soaking and soil drenching, and their subsequent effects on plant physiological traits, including height, dry biomass, and chlorophyll content. Both isolates successfully colonized maize tissues, with the highest colonization frequency observed in roots following soil drenching, which aligns with previous findings highlighting that plants appear to recognize EEPF as symbionts, permitting entry via natural openings and direct penetration with minimal resistance, and

the recovery usually being highest close to the application site (Bamisile *et al.*, 2018). Despite successful colonization, no significant differences were observed between treated and control plants regarding height and shoot dry biomass. However, *M. robertsii* isolates 75 significantly enhanced chlorophyll accumulations when applied via soil drenching, suggesting a potential physiological benefit that could be linked to improved photosynthetic efficiency. Similar findings have been reported for various EEPF species, including *M. anisopliae*, *M. brunneum*, *B. bassiana*, and *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, which have demonstrated growth-promoting effects across multiple crops (Jaber and Enkerli, 2016, and Garrido-Jurado *et al.*, 2017). For instance, *M. robertsii* seed inoculation was found to enhance maize growth and vigor (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020), while *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* applications improved foliar biomass and yield in maize (Kabaluk and Ericsson, 2007 and Liao *et al.*, 2014). These beneficial effects are often attributed to enhanced nutrient uptake, hormonal modulation, and stress tolerance induced by fungal metabolites (Behie and Bidochka,

2014; Jiang *et al.*, 2022; Tomilova *et al.*, 2023 and Tyurin *et al.*, 2023).

The success of EEPF colonization and its impact on host physiology are strongly influenced by inoculation method, fungal strain, and host plant species (Posada *et al.*, 2007 and Bamisile *et al.*, 2018). For example, *B. bassiana* exhibited optimal colonization via foliar application in sorghum, stem injection in coffee, and root dipping in tomato, whereas Tefera and Vidal (2009), reported effective colonization of sorghum by *B. bassiana* across multiple inoculation methods. These findings highlight that the compatibility between fungal isolates and plant hosts is highly context-dependent, and selecting an appropriate inoculation strategy is essential for ensuring consistent colonization and functional outcomes.

The endophytic entomopathogenic role of *Metarhizium* spp. further enhances their value in integrated pest management (IPM) strategies. *Metarhizium* spp. can persist in the soil and within plants as endophytes, providing long-term suppression of pests such as *S. frugiperda*. Previous studies demonstrated that *S. frugiperda* larvae feeding on endophyte-colonized plants exhibit reduced weight gain, delayed development, and diminished fecundity (Altaf *et al.*, 2023). These findings are consistent with the current study, where neonates feeding on maize plants colonized by *M. robertsii* isolates 50 and 75 exhibited significantly lower weight gain compared to the control. Similarly, the weight gain of *S. littoralis* larvae fed on leaves infected with endophytic fungi was reduced compared with controls. Furthermore, protease and lipase activities in the gut of *S. littoralis* decreased with increasing concentrations of fungus applied to plants. An increase in phenol oxidase activity in the gut also indicated an increased defense response of larvae feeding on Beauveria-infected leaves (Darsouei *et al.*, 2024). The underlying mechanisms by which EEPF affect arthropod herbivores are poorly understood. However, various mechanisms have been

suggested, such as the production and modulation of plants of secondary metabolites, including phenolic compounds, which are an important class of plant secondary metabolites, deter herbivores by reducing palatability, exhibiting direct toxicity against insects (Simmonds, 2006; Wu *et al.*, 2016 and War *et al.*, 2019), or interfering with digestive processes by inhibiting enzyme activities necessary for digestion (War *et al.*, 2012). In the same context, Shrivastava *et al.* (2015), demonstrated that plants inoculated with *B. bassiana* exhibited higher levels of terpenoids, secondary metabolites known for their antiherbivore properties.

Overall, the dual role of *M. robertsii* as both a plant symbiont and an entomopathogen underscores its potential for sustainable pest management. Its endophytic establishment not only contributes to plant physiological enhancement, such as increased chlorophyll synthesis, but also indirectly affects herbivore performance, likely through biochemical changes in host plant tissues and altered volatile emissions that interfere with insect feeding and behavior, as demonstrated in our previous research. These findings support the concept of leveraging EEPF as multifunctional agents that simultaneously promote plant health and suppress pest populations, offering a promising, environmentally sustainable alternative to conventional chemical control measures.

M. robertsii was successfully established as an endophyte in maize without adversely affecting plant growth parameters. Fungal colonization enhanced chlorophyll content and reduced *S. frugiperda* larval performance, suggesting improved plant vigor and induced defense. These findings highlight the potential of *M. robertsii* as a dual-function symbiont, contributing both to plant health and pest suppression. Further investigation into the molecular and physiological mechanisms underlying these effects is warranted.

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